

Cahill Design Consultants:

Implementing client-facing AI into
a specialist construction consultancy

BridgeAI

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

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Implementing client-facing AI into a specialist construction consultancy

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Topic overview

This case study explores how **Cahill Design Consultants** (CDC), a specialist construction consultancy founded in 2014, is integrating AI into its client-facing workflows. Originally focused on fire engineering and acoustic design, CDC has grown into a multidisciplinary consultancy serving contractors, architects, and major construction projects. Participation in Bridge AI – The Turing Way Practitioners Hub has supported CDC’s technical and ethical knowhow as it develops an AI-powered reporting assistant designed to enable clients to navigate complex technical documents more efficiently, while maintaining rigorous safeguards around accuracy and data security.

From internal efficiencies to client-facing AI

CDC began its AI implementation journey by asking how the company could use emerging, widely accessible techniques to streamline its processes. “Initially, it was about raising awareness internally and understanding what AI could realistically do for us,” says Sarah Pittard, Marketing and Communications Executive at CDC and a Practitioners Hub Expert-in-Residence. “We’re a small company, and our technical teams are very busy day to day, so we looked at ways we could use generative AI tools to save some time. As our understanding of the technology grew, we started thinking about how it could improve our service to clients.” For CDC, this began with ‘easy wins’ such as taking meeting minutes, but soon developed to incorporate tasks including reviewing reports for formatting inconsistencies, comparing reports to the original scope of work, and reviewing legal contracts against standard terms and conditions – areas in which AI could do the heavy lifting before human review.

This then led to an idea for a client-facing use case. CDC's engineers produce detailed technical reports that can take a long time to work through. Clients often come back with multiple questions for the engineers – but in many cases the answers are readily available in the report. Could an AI interface guide clients towards the relevant parts of their reports to reduce bottlenecks and avoid taking valuable time away from the engineers?

An AI-powered report assistant

The result is a secure, client-facing AI solution that functions as an enhanced chatbot within a controlled portal environment. The platform allows authorised clients to:

- upload and access specific project reports
- ask natural-language questions about the content
- receive answers grounded strictly in that document
- see page-number citations showing evidence of where each answer originates.

The intention is not to provide new advice, but to clarify and signpost expert-produced information already contained in the report. As one client remarked during testing of the solution: "It was easy to navigate, intuitive, and provided useful clarifications. I didn't feel like I was getting advice, but I did feel it confirmed my understanding." This distinction is critical in technical disciplines such as fire safety engineering, where accuracy and regulatory compliance are paramount.

From a technical perspective, the system uses a retrieval-augmented generation architecture (RAG), combining two commercial AI models for distinct purposes. RAG can improve AI-generated responses by pulling in relevant, trusted information from external sources – such as company documents or databases – rather than relying solely on a model's training data, helping to reduce inaccuracies and hallucinations.

Each page of a CDC PDF report is first processed by Anthropic's Claude LLM to extract text, read tables and describe visual elements such as diagrams or charts. Extracted information is then split into chunks using OpenAI's vector embedding API, which converts each section into a numerical form that captures its overall meaning.

When a user submits a question, it is converted into a vector and matched against the stored embeddings to retrieve the most relevant document passages. These passages are passed on to Claude, which generates an answer grounded specifically in the uploaded document and includes page-number references.

Crucially, the system does not rely on general training data when answering queries. It retrieves context from the specific uploaded report before generating a response. If relevant information cannot be found within the document, the system is designed to acknowledge this rather than to produce an answer regardless. The tool is also trained to respond only within the engineering scope of the report and will not answer unrelated or spurious questions (for example, recommendations for tourist activities in the project site location). It operates as part of a secure, login-controlled portal to ensure confidentiality and compliance with NDAs and client data protections.

Early signals suggest the platform could save 2 hours per week for each consultant, equivalent to an annual revenue of £100,000.

Challenges: Time, expertise and internal adoption

CDC encountered two major hurdles early in the development process. First, as a small consultancy, dedicating internal resources to this type of innovation proved difficult: developing a sophisticated AI tool requires a high degree of employees' time alongside their ongoing commitments. Second, while CDC's engineers are experts in their own domains, they do not necessarily have the technical knowledge and skills to build a secure AI platform.

The company therefore chose to partner with a local AI development firm, The AI Guys, which has worked with CDC on this project for over six months. "We're very pleased with our decision to outsource the development work – particularly to a locally based company," says Mark Scaife, Commercial Director at CDC and a Practitioners Hub Expert-in-Residence. "The AI Guys have worked closely with us to make sure all our concerns around the accuracy and safety of the product have been fully considered. The process has worked really well – they understood our scope and needs straight away, and it's been brilliant to see the different iterations of the platform improve over time."

To help with building confidence and ensuring accuracy, the platform underwent extensive internal testing before selected clients were invited to take part in a subsequent testing phase. CDC deliberately included both AI-savvy users and those with limited exposure to AI technologies to understand a broad range of perspectives. CDC also set up a dedicated staff AI channel on Microsoft Teams and held hands-on workshops to allow colleagues to explore AI tools and potential use cases in a safe, open environment.

“The internal engagement side of things was really important to us,” adds Sarah. “And to be honest it was probably a bit harder than we’d expected. It’s not that people were resistant to learning about AI or introducing it, but there was a lot of work for us to do to help people see the benefits and how it could impact their job role in a positive way. The workshops and testing helped with that and provided an opportunity for colleagues to contribute to the project and make the platform as useful as possible.”

Next steps: Refinement, feedback, and working towards a launch

Sarah explains that the focus now is on refining the platform through continued collaboration with The AI Guys, ahead of wider rollout. Iteration has been central to the process so far, and that approach will continue as the team reviews the solution’s performance, strengthens its safeguards, and responds to client feedback as part of the ongoing second phase of testing. Particular attention is being paid to the prevention of hallucinations and maintaining strong cyber security and confidentiality controls. Meanwhile, features under development include a built-in feedback mechanism to capture user experience more efficiently and identify areas for improvement.

Looking further ahead, CDC intends to explore additional AI-enabled services that can support both internal efficiency and client engagement. Sarah adds: “It feels like a big achievement for quite a small company like ours, which didn’t have in-house AI technical expertise, to now be in a position where we are a lot more confident and have an AI platform that looks in really good shape. We hope that this is just the starting point and opens up a lot more opportunities for us.”

The CDC team believes its path to AI adoption is repeatable and accessible for other report-generating businesses in the built environment sector, following a five-step process:

- 1. Build cultural readiness**
(demystify AI across your team).
- 2. Identify the pinch points**
(find where repetition costs you most).
- 3. Engage structured support**
(such as The Turing Way Practitioners Hub).
- 4. Collaborate with specialists**
(partner externally where internal capacity is limited).
- 5. Prioritise responsible AI**
(ethical, secure and standards-aligned from day one).

Reflections on *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub

“It has been a brilliant experience. At the beginning, the amount we didn’t know about AI implementation seemed quite overwhelming, but going through all of the different sessions with the Practitioners Hub has helped us ask the right questions and build our own solution on solid foundations. The interactive workshops – especially the sessions on AI user personas and AI challenges and consequences – really made me think about how different people might view and interact with the system we’re creating at CDC. Hearing from the experts and from participants in other sectors with very different levels of AI experience was invaluable and has given us confidence in our own platform and also how we approach AI more generally.”

Sara Pittard,

Marketing and Communications Executive
at Cahill Design Consultants

Key takeaways

- Chatbot-style AI systems can allow businesses to streamline elements of their client engagement and communication, freeing up specialists to focus on work that cannot be automated.
- Guardrails are essential – especially in high-stakes and regulated fields such as fire safety. These guardrails can include retrieval-based systems that ground responses in specific documents, and rigorous training and configuration to reduce the risk of hallucinations or inaccuracies.
- While the robust technical development of an AI system is undoubtedly crucial, internal engagement and education among employees cannot be overlooked as a vital factor in successful AI adoption.
- Where resources allow, small firms can benefit from partnering with specialist external AI developers to bridge time and capability gaps.
- Participation in collaborative technical and ethical communities such as The Turing Way Practitioners Hub can improve skills and increase confidence.

Contributors and acknowledgements

This case study is published under *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub* 2025-26 Cohort – case study series. The Practitioners Hub is *The Turing Way* project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2025, The Turing Way team welcomed **Mark Scaife, Sarah Pittard, and Lee Parkin from Cahill Design Consultants** as Experts-in-Residence to discuss and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI as well as build additional skills around best practices in responsible, ethical, and collaborative working. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2025-26 Cohort was co-delivered by **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher – Open Source Practices and Dr Ann Borda, Senior Research Community Manager. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager. **Ann Borda** is the Case Study Liaison for this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Malvika Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: theturingway@gmail.com

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